

Pedagogy and Artificial Intelligence

Preliminary Considerations on Integrating Study Methods with AI

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ABSTRACT

Artificial intelligence, particularly in its generative form, represents a technological and cultural breakthrough of immense impact, poised to transform every aspect of human activity, including education. In this article, we will explore its application in the educational field, highlighting its potential beyond the criticisms—more or less justified—that have been raised. Far from being merely a tool for copying assignments, AI can support students in learning, making even the most complex topics easier to understand. After a brief analysis of the main challenges, we will focus on the numerous opportunities this technology offers to the world of education.¹

Some Limits and Challenges of artificial intelligence in education

Among the many domains in which artificial intelligence is now being applied, the educational sphere is undoubtedly one of the most significant. Although current systems still have technical limitations – which are expected to be overcome over time – their potential is considerable and deserves our full attention. On this topic, an enormous amount has already been said, and discussion is ongoing, with questions that constantly intersect: ethical, social, theoretical and political issues. Within the space of this brief contribution, it is not possible to address such a variety of questions. Instead, in line with the aims of the title of this pa-

per, I will focus exclusively on some of the main didactic and pedagogical challenges raised by AI.

It is widely acknowledged that, if not integrated thoughtfully, AI can have certain negative consequences for students' cognitive and relational development. In this regard, one of the main risks – according to many who oppose the use of AI in schools – concerns the potential weakening of critical and independent thinking. When students rely on ready-made solutions provided by AI, they may lose the opportunity to exercise their own reasoning and to tackle problems with independence and creativity. The capacity for analysis and reflection is refined through engagement with complex situations and through the elaboration of

personal solutions; these are activities that risk being pushed into the background when immediate, standardized answers are readily available.

Moreover, the intensive use of AI risks promoting a superficial form of learning. The speed with which answers are delivered may induce students to focus on the final result, neglecting the logical path that leads to the solution. This “shortcut” approach can therefore limit an accurate understanding of concepts and of the relations between concepts, undermining the construction of solid and lasting knowledge.

Another critical aspect is the possible decline in problem-solving skills. Constant reliance on tools that provide instant answers may fail to stimulate the development of robust strategies for solving problems. Yet the ability to face new situations, to adapt one’s knowledge and to experiment with different methodological approaches is fundamental to a well-rounded education, and it is honed by engaging with challenges that demand active effort. In addition, some critics argue that the intensive use of AI can lead to a loss of interaction and empathy among students, and between students and teachers. Traditional educational experience does not rest solely on the transmission of information, but also on the relationship between teachers and learners. Educators do not simply convey knowledge: they also play a key role in motivating, inspiring and emotionally supporting students, tailoring the learning path to each learner’s specific needs. Human interaction fosters dialogue, exchange and shared reflection – elements that are difficult to replicate in an automated system.

A further problem is the risk of fostering a passive mode of learning. If information generated by AI becomes the student’s main source of knowledge, the educational experience may lose that dynamic and interactive character which stimulates active and engaged learning. Education is, in fact, grounded in direct involvement, in discussion and in the personal elaboration of knowledge: processes that risk being undermined or, at

the very least, impoverished if AI replaces the active path of discovery and critical questioning.

Finally, the massive use of AI could promote an excessive standardisation and superficiality of learning. A “one size fits all” approach fails to take account of cognitive diversity, of different learning styles and of students’ individual specificities. Teaching must be capable of valuing each learner’s unique path, adapting to their specific needs and promoting creativity. A system based exclusively on standardized procedures risks homogenizing the educational experience, limiting the potential for personal and critical development.

All these points partially overlap – one need only think of the connections between the difficulties in problem-solving, the risk of passivity and the shallowness of learning – yet they also have their own specific features, which is why I have chosen to describe them separately.

Other risks concern possible errors and the reliability of the information provided, as well as violations of privacy, the security of personal data and the danger of plagiarism, and so on. These are problems of AI in general (not specific to education) and, even if they are likely to be mitigated as technology advances – at a very rapid pace, moreover – we cannot afford to ignore them at the current state of the art.

In conclusion, although Artificial Intelligence offers innovative and powerful tools to support study, it is essential to consider its limits carefully from a didactic and pedagogical point of view. It is precisely an awareness of these limits of AI, and of artificial intelligence in educational contexts, that enables us to make “intelligent” use of it, to propose appropriate safeguards and to teach students how to use it in a genuinely beneficial way.

Internal vs. External Motivation

All the time saved thanks to artificial intelligence should be reinvested in exploring subjects more deeply, moving more slowly but with greater

awareness. This, however, is truly possible only for those who see studying first and foremost as a form of personal growth. In the reality of the school system, by contrast, artificial intelligence—thanks to its ability to process large amounts of information very quickly—is increasingly used to “copy” homework. This phenomenon emerges especially among students who let themselves be guided exclusively by external incentives such as grades, social recognition, and school-related pressure. In such cases, AI becomes a shortcut to avoid the effort required for genuine learning, replacing personal engagement with ready-made answers.

A fundamental aspect of learning is precisely students’ motivation, which cannot be based solely on extrinsic factors. Deci and Ryan’s *Self-Determination Theory* highlights the importance of intrinsic motivation, that inner drive that leads one to study out of curiosity, personal enjoyment, or a desire for self-improvement. When students focus only on the final outcome and act out of fear of a bad grade or in search of others’ approval, the educational process risks becoming superficial and mechanical, preventing the development of critical skills such as problem-solving strategies and analytical thinking.

Students learn best when they perceive three key elements in their educational journey: 1) Autonomy: the opportunity to make choices and feel like active agents in their own learning; 2) Competence: the sense of being capable of facing challenges and progressively improving through their own effort; 3) Relatedness (Meaningful Relationships): the support of teachers, tutors, and classmates in an environment that values each person’s contribution.

For this reason, instructional design that integrates AI must go beyond simply achieving external goals, and instead create activities that spark curiosity, critical thinking, and a genuine interest in knowledge. Ultimately, relying on AI to copy homework is equivalent to giving up the opportunity to learn actively and to build a solid cultural foundation. Yet once this danger has been

identified, it is artificial intelligence itself that can help us overcome it, as I will show in what follows.

Motivation is not something entirely separate from study methods; on the contrary, the goals that drive us to study are decisive for the kind of study method we adopt. If I study with deep motivation and personal commitment, I will use study methods that foster long-term learning. If, conversely, my sole purpose is to pass an oral exam or a test, I will tend to use methods that favor the short- to medium-term assimilation of large amounts of information.

Even from this point of view, AI can act as a stimulus toward the right way to study: identifying—or giving oneself—intrinsic motivations for studying is, in an era already dominated by AI, an increasingly urgent necessity. AI is showing us all the limits of a purely extrinsic motivation for studying: this is not a limitation of AI, but of our own, and the fact that AI brings it to light nudges us to find personal reasons to study—the only reasons that truly work in the long run.

From Wanting Only the Result to Focusing on the Process

A student who uses artificial intelligence passively, merely to have it do their homework, will inevitably end up focusing on the result. The teacher’s role therefore becomes crucial in guiding the student to shift their attention from the mere result to the process. This is the fundamental principle that must be kept clearly in mind: shifting the focus from the result to the process, so as to transform interest in studying from something external and superficial into an inner, conscious process.

The process is the study method, and the study method is the process—or rather, it is the structure of the learning process. This is what we mean when we recommend moving forward one step at a time, focusing on each step along the way: bringing attention back to the process and not to the result. One of the most important differ-

ences between a student who uses artificial intelligence passively and one who uses it actively lies precisely in this: the former concentrates on the result, whereas the latter uses AI to engage personally and independently with the entire learning process.ⁱⁱ

One of the most effective instructional tools for countering the passive use of AI and refocusing students' attention from the result to the process is the use of immediate feedback, or feedback that is as minimally mediated as possible (a topic we will explore further in the following pages). Let us consider an example: a teacher assigns their students some quadratic equations to work on at home. The teacher will give them in canonical form ($ax^2+bx+c=0$) for instance the equation " $6x^2+7x+3=0$ ". The teacher will also specify that the equations are to be solved using the quadratic formula ($x_{1,2} = [-b \pm \sqrt{(b^2 - 4ac)}] / 2a$). Let us assume that the student has AI solve this equation and then simply copies the procedure and the results that AI provides. The student will be under the illusion that they have "achieved the result" (that is, completed the assignment, because for them the assignment is the "result"). The next day in class, however, the student will be given other equations—this time not in canonical form, meaning they must be simplified and reduced to quadratic equations in standard form, such as " $6x^2 + 3x^2 + 7x - 4x + 3 = 0$ " or other, even more complex equations. The student will be allowed to keep on their desk only the simpler homework assignment they completed the previous day at home (with the help of artificial intelligence). At that point, whether or not the student manages to solve the new equations, they will be forced to shift their attention from the result to the process. This type of feedback is not immediate, but it is close enough in time to the initial stimulus (the homework assigned the day before) to compel the student to reorient themselves toward the process—that is, toward the study method and procedural thinking that must be developed and intensively trained in formal subjects such as mathematics.

At that stage, immediate feedback must follow on the second, more complex in-class assignment. This feedback should consist essentially of the teacher's critical but constructive assessment, accompanied by explanations aimed less at correcting the result and more at redirecting the student's attention. And, still within the context of this example (and therefore not necessarily to be universalized), if that assessment is to be expressed as a grade, it should refer only to the in-class assignment (immediate feedback), not to the homework (mediated or nearly immediate feedback).

Attention is the first step in helping students become aware of themselves and of their relationship to studying. A statement like this may seem almost trivial, but it is not. If we truly want to achieve results with students—especially with those who are more challenging to engage—we must also learn, as teachers and educators, to think in terms of processes rather than results. Returning to the previous example, the simple fact that, after the second in-class assignment, the student understands that what they did the day before at home with the passive use of AI was essentially pointless, represents a step forward—not yet in the study process itself, but in the awareness that must accompany every voluntary and internally motivated learning process.

If, as is often said, every form of learning is a form of self-directed learning, then the first step is to shift the student's attention from the result to the path. When we talk about gamification in learning (another topic explored in the following pages), this is, first of all, what we must do: shift and focus attention on a specific point (the action in a video game and the specific topic to be learned in studying) through immediate or almost immediate feedback. When a teenager plays a video game, they are certainly aware of the goal they want to achieve (for example, completing a level), yet their attention is fully concentrated on the action they must perform in the here and now. So, however difficult and, in some cases, seem-

ingly impossible, this is the direction in which we must move: the difficulty of the second day is a desirable difficulty—an obstacle that is indeed somewhat challenging, but not impossible to overcome. Exactly as in a game, each level is a bit more difficult than the previous one, yet still manageable: if a game has ten levels, you will not be allowed to jump straight from the first to the last; you will have to climb the ladder one rung at a time.

The theory of *desirable difficulties* was developed by psychologists Robert Bjork and Elizabeth Bjork. It holds that learning and long-term memory improve when we encounter obstacles and challenges during the learning process, rather than when learning is made as easy as possible. Video games are an excellent example of how this theory can be applied, but the strategic use of AI in education can also become such an example—and it can do so all the more effectively as the student shifts their focus from the result to the process.

Just a Tool

The subject of this study is the relationship between artificial intelligence and teaching, within the school context and, by extension, also beyond it. Its primary focus, however, remains school education: in this setting, AI is considered above all as a tool. This does not mean, of course, reducing artificial intelligence to a mere technical aid. In the broader framework of human society, AI is far more than that: in all likelihood, it represents one of the greatest inventions in history. Not only because of its versatility and the extraordinary results it makes possible, but because it has altered the very paradigm of invention: if humanity has so far created tools, today—with AI—it makes a “quantum” leap (in a metaphorical sense). This is no longer simply yet another technology capable of simplifying complex activities, but rather an entity (I do not know what else to call it, although I am aware that the term evokes Neoplatonic reminiscences) that, while grounded in physical reality

and built through computational, engineering, logical, and mathematical-statistical means, manages to replicate—at least in part—the operational functioning of human intelligence, enormously amplifying its reach.

The attainment of AGI and, prospectively, forms of superintelligence—should it occur (and many believe it is not a distant milestone)—would have disruptive effects: it would transform the world of work, reshape society in every respect, and even affect the very way we conceive of human individuality. These are, however, questions that exceed the boundaries of the present discussion.

Here, as far as I am concerned, AI will therefore be considered as a tool for study and teaching, without renouncing the ideal of humanity that must be constantly cultivated in each person and in all. If that ideal weakens or is neglected, the risk of a destructive drift concerns human coexistence as a whole—regardless of artificial intelligence.

Having made this necessary clarification, let us continue our narrative, starting again from the fact that the balance between the use of technology and human interaction—as well as the promotion of active, critical learning—represents the key to fully harnessing AI’s potential without compromising the quality and depth of education. In this regard, it is worth noting that many of the criticisms and considerations just outlined were also directed at the spread of personal computers and later the internet, and finally at cell phones. If we look further back, the model (or, with poetic license, we might even call it the archetype) of this kind of critique was already present in antiquity: we find it in Socrates’ criticism of writing, as reported by Plato in the *Phaedrus*. In a nutshell: every technological innovation that “lightens” the mind’s load in carrying out a task ends up atrophying it. This criticism contains much truth, but at the same time it overlooks the opportunities that a tool offers and that, instead of atrophying our abilities, can actually help us develop them.

The negative aspects of AI—from the reduction of critical thinking to superficial learning—can be overcome by calibrating its use and clearly defining its role. AI should not be regarded as the solution to the problems of teaching, but rather as a support, an aid; and like any tool, its value depends on how it is used. If it is integrated in a balanced way, alongside human instruction and active teaching methods, AI will enhance learning without undermining students' autonomy, creativity, and engagement. In other words, the key lies in recognizing that the limitations described above are not intrinsic to the technology itself, but arise from its excessive or poorly calibrated use; on the contrary, when used appropriately, AI can become a valuable ally for educational success.

Expecting AI to replace and remedy the problems of everyday teaching in our schools is an expectation that moves in the direction of making instruction even more passive and standardized. The work of educators who make use of such innovative tools, by contrast, can and should move precisely in the opposite direction: counteracting the homogenization and flattening of learning. If it is true that a crude, careless use of AI exposes us to this risk, it is equally true that a thoughtful, targeted, and carefully delimited use can help—without “side effects”—all students and, in particular, those who experience greater difficulties in learning.

In reality, Artificial Intelligence is also something more than a tool (that is, it is an active tool that can act and create content independently of the will and intelligence of its user), and already today it makes it possible to support students in a highly active and constructive way. AI is a tool capable of providing immediate and semantically relevant feedback, at least when that feedback is correctly interpreted by the person using it. A shovel is a tool for working the soil, but the shovel itself does not give you feedback on how you are using it; it does not explain to you how the soil should be turned. Artificial intelligence, to stay

with the metaphor, does. And this is what students should do right from the start: not merely use AI as if it were a highly specialized, generative search engine, but learn to manage it actively. If, for example, a virtual tutor can be designed to personalize lessons based on each student's needs, identifying gaps and providing targeted explanations, the student in turn can assume an active role in their own educational path. Consider the case of a summary of a book chapter to be presented to the teacher. The student should not simply ask a chatbot to generate it straightaway and then proceed to correct, modify, or supplement it. A more effective approach involves a three-step process.

First step (independent production): the student attempts to write the summary without any support, relying on their own abilities.

Second step (comparison and improvement): only after completing this first attempt does the student use artificial intelligence to refine their work, asking for suggestions or comparing it with a version generated by AI.

Third step (critical review): finally, the student carefully examines the AI-generated version, applying critical thinking and close attention in order to verify its accuracy and integrate it into their own work in a deliberate, thoughtful way.

This method helps maximize the effectiveness of integrating AI with traditional study, strengthening the student's analytical and reasoning skills. Thus, on closer inspection, AI is both a tool and something more: it is like a mirror intelligence (referring metaphorically to mirror neurons), in which our natural intelligence is reflected, and the image that emerges can, each time and over time, be modified, improved, and updated.

A Valuable Resource for Students, Teachers, Educators, and Parents

In our elementary and secondary schools, the educational process goes beyond the simple two-way relationship between teachers and students: it takes shape as a complex network of relationships

that also involves parents and other entities, such as study support services offered by local administrations. In this context, AI can prove to be a valuable aid for all these stakeholders, provided they play an active and constructive role in the educational process.

Especially in the case of elementary school, the first aspect to consider is the potential of AI for personalized instruction and flexibility. Precisely because artificial intelligence can be “queried,” it allows us to frame questions in such a way as to obtain answers tailored to our own (or others’) needs. Every child is unique, with different learning paces, styles, and needs. Thanks to its ability to adapt to individual peculiarities, AI makes it possible to design a personalized learning path. Through applications that analyze each student’s skills and areas for improvement, AI can offer customized exercises, explanations, and activities, thereby ensuring that every child can progress according to their own abilities. This personalized approach not only supports the acquisition of knowledge, but also fosters self-confidence and motivation.

The personalization enabled by AI can also serve as a powerful tool for social equity. Imagine a student who has an internet connection but whose family cannot afford private remedial lessons: thanks to AI, that student can access detailed explanations, personalized exercises, and immediate feedback, thus bridging—or at least narrowing—the educational gap with peers from more affluent families. In this way, AI offers all students the opportunity to move forward in their educational journey, promoting equal access to learning resources and contributing to a more just and inclusive society.

There is no doubt that artificial intelligence makes it possible to save time. Thanks to AI, students can (and increasingly will be able to, as technology improves) obtain immediate and accurate answers, eliminating the need for lengthy searches in books or on the web. This time savings can allow students to focus more on understanding

concepts and on practice, thereby supporting more effective learning. In addition, teachers can use these tools to enrich their lessons, reserving more time for interactive and in-depth activities.

As I noted at the beginning, the time spent searching for information and for explanations best suited to our needs is not time wasted, but an integral part of the learning process. However, this is not always the case. Let me give an example that will be immediately clear to anyone who studied foreign languages before the advent of personal computers and the internet: hours and hours spent searching for the translation of terms in dictionaries or trying to understand idiomatic expressions. In cases like these, and many others, the use of AI can only be beneficial.

Another interesting aspect of using AI in education is its ability to make studying more engaging. Through interactive quizzes, educational games, and simulations, AI—whether via chatbots or dedicated applications—introduces playful elements into the learning process, helping to stimulate students’ curiosity. This approach, known as *gamification*, can make studying more enjoyable and promote the assimilation of knowledge in a dynamic, interactive context. “As for the term gamification, I think it is appropriate to offer a clarification: we should have the courage—just as English speakers did when they coined it—to introduce an Italian neologism, *aggiocamento*.”ⁱⁱⁱ This idea is not mine, but that of Prof. Alberto Peruzzi, and I fully agree with it and find it extremely meaningful. It is not merely a terminological question, nor only a matter of preserving the value of the Italian language (which, in my view, must always and increasingly be safeguarded, not only because it is our language, but above all because it is beautiful). Above all, it is because this word, *aggiocamento*, aptly conveys the idea of “ap-pren-di-men-to” (learning) through the logic and cognitive structure exercised in the “gio-co” (game). For these reasons, from this point on in this article, I will replace the term gamification with *aggiocamento*.

Some prefer to use the term *ludicizzazione*, but I do not find it particularly fitting. In fact, the goal is not simply to make studying more “playful,” but—as already mentioned—to leverage in studying those same psycho-cognitive aspects of play that make it so appealing.

What I am about to discuss now is, in my view, the most important aspect. Artificial intelligence, when properly queried, proves to be a very useful tool for filling students’ gaps in knowledge and understanding. While books and online tutorials can sometimes leave certain concepts unclear, AI provides clear and detailed answers, responding specifically to the questions asked. This targeted approach enables users to identify precisely the areas in which they need further clarification, thereby facilitating the learning process. In summary, AI not only explains each topic in depth, but also guides students in resolving their doubts, making education more accessible and more selective.

From personal experience, I find AI extremely helpful in learning mathematics. Textbooks and tutorials all too often take for granted certain details in mathematical explanations which, if omitted, can block the student, who no longer sees the logical connection between one step and the next. In these and many other cases, the student has the opportunity to do many exercises on the same topics and to obtain additional information that can spark their curiosity.

Active–Passive

The student who uses AI to do their homework with simple “copy and paste,” as already noted, is only doing harm to themselves. They might as well use that time for more rewarding leisure activities. But even here I want to identify a positive element and highlight one of those aspects I referred to earlier but did not explain: AI’s ability to imitate human thinking—especially when it comes to tests, exams, assessment procedures, and so on—could become an opportunity to question not so much artificial intelligence itself as those very

standardized assessment tools that have become increasingly homogenized, superficial, and inconclusive.

In other words, AI’s ability to imitate human thinking is a way of bringing to light an intrinsic contradiction in those assessment instruments on which the school system (and not only the school system) rests. After all, we should not complain if artificial intelligence manages to “out-smart” tests and exams, given that these very tests and exams were conceived and designed on the basis of the same principles that “govern” computing: standardization, univocity, homogenization. For quite some time now, national and international tests have been produced with the (now indispensable) support of digital technology and even AI.

Is it really reasonable, then, to complain that the “end user” who relies on artificial intelligence is cheating on tests that were themselves created with the help of artificial intelligence? The vicious circle is obvious. Less obvious, however, is the mistaken perspective from which certain innovative tools are viewed. We look only at the “shortcut” or “facilitation” that the tool provides, and we fail to focus on the vast range of possibilities that technology makes available.

If it is true that a chatbot can produce an almost flawless Latin translation, thereby deceiving the teacher and effectively preventing any real learning from taking place, it is equally true that we often overlook the possibilities that the “machine” offers for practice: the opportunity to question it in order to explore variants, consider possible alternative interpretations, and develop paraphrases and periphrases of a given text.

From AI as Simulator to Aggiocamento in Learning.

Using a chatbot based on artificial intelligence as a simulator for oral examinations has the potential to revolutionize studying, bringing to light mechanisms that, if leveraged properly, make learning more effective, motivating, and personalized.

When integrated into teaching, AI can transform the educational experience into a playful (“gamified”) path—literally, a game-like experience—structured as a sequence of interconnected “quests,” as in a role-playing game (a topic to which we will return shortly), rich in challenges, immediate feedback, and “rewards” that now take on educational meaning.

To illustrate how fruitful this approach can be for teaching, I will outline some specific uses below, while immediately stressing that it should not be confused with the mere “gamifying” of study (as if it were a fun and light pastime, a kind of “playful trotting” of the mind, as some contemporary educators would have it). *Aggiocamento*, as it is understood here, is something quite different: it consists in transferring into the educational sphere those cognitive processes that work extremely well in video games to foster learning and concentration. In other words, it is a matter of making profitable use of the very cognitive “laws” that make role-playing video games so compelling.

Instructional Design and Personalized Challenges. Let us imagine mastery of each topic of study as a mission to be completed: AI can adjust the level of difficulty to match individual skills, turning every mistake into an opportunity for growth. Just as in video games, where a difficult challenge pushes the player to refine their abilities, AI can propose exercises that stretch the student, guiding them along a path of continuous improvement. Moreover, just as in a video game there are different ways to overcome a challenge depending on the abilities selected for one’s character, so too the personalization of problem-solving strategies not only highlights each learner’s unique strengths, but also turns studying into a custom-tailored adventure. This is also an excellent method for identifying and overcoming gaps in knowledge that often block students.

Notifications and Constant Stimuli. In the digital world, we are used to receiving notifications that capture our attention and spark curiosity.

In a similar way, AI applied to education can use targeted notifications to keep students’ motivation high. When properly designed, these signals tap into the phenomenon of novelty bias—the tendency to give more weight to what is new—turning each update into an incentive to continue along the learning path.

Immediate Feedback and Intelligent Suggestions. One of AI’s strengths is its ability to provide immediate, detailed feedback. Just as in video games, where every wrong move is instantly recognizable as such and can be corrected so the player can refine their strategies, AI offers timely responses and intelligent suggestions that allow students to understand exactly where improvement is needed.

This immediacy favors the release of dopamine—the brain’s “feel-good” chemical—making each success, even in studying, an additional reason to move forward enthusiastically. In studying as we traditionally conceive it (for example, reading and reviewing at home, being tested in class), feedback is almost always too far removed from the moment of effort. Even when you receive a positive grade on an assignment, you receive it at a temporal distance that is too great from the moment you actually did the work.

Our brain, however, in order to learn effectively and over the long term, needs immediate feedback: the knowledge acquired must “stabilize” in memory, and the possibility of obtaining an immediate response about whether what you are learning is correct or not, complete or not, and so on, greatly facilitates memorization. This possibility is now available to us through AI.

Interactive and Multisensory Learning. *Aggiocamento* carries with it the idea of learning that engages all the senses: simulations, timed quizzes, animated mind maps, and even virtual reality turn studying into a dynamic and visual experience. This multisensory approach not only stimulates memory but also makes the learning process more engaging than passive reading of a book. The abil-

ity to interact with content in a multimodal way promotes deeper and more lasting understanding.

Compelling Goals and Escalation. Artificial intelligence can be programmed to define stimulating educational goals: achievable yet challenging targets that avoid triviality and keep motivation high. Through progressively more complex tasks, AI creates a sense of escalation, where each level mastered reinforces the student’s sense of command over what they are studying.

As the learner advances, the AI system proposes tests and questions calibrated to individual needs, turning each goal achieved into a concrete step toward the final objective. This gradual increase in difficulty allows students to measure their progress in a tangible way, making learning not only more effective but also more satisfying and stimulating. Every challenge overcome confirms ongoing personal growth, keeping attention and interest in study alive.

At this point, however, it is necessary to make a more general observation: *aggiornamento* in studying also presents some drawbacks and therefore must be approached with caution. For example, escalation in learning (unlike in video games) always goes hand in hand with an “addition of content”—more material to know, which is often structurally different from what has been learned before. It is not just a matter of progressively increasing the level of difficulty: as difficulty rises, in studying there is also an increase in the amount and type of things to be learned.

Finally, in studying, the cognitive load—because of the intellectual effort required—is much higher than that demanded by a video game, and it varies in terms of abstraction from one topic to another. By contrast, in games, the “abstractive” effort is almost always constant, unidirectional, and of a “programmed” intensity.

Ongoing Practice Without Stress. One of the most evident benefits of using AI is the possibility of practicing in an environment free of pressure. Without the anxiety associated with being tested, students can explore and deepen topics un-

til they truly feel prepared, developing a sense of confidence that supports learning. This continuous, pressure-free practice makes it easier to overcome difficulties as they arise, avoiding the embarrassment of public mistakes and encouraging steady growth in understanding.

Suspense and Cliffhangers. Finally, the element of suspense plays a key role in keeping students “hooked” into their learning path. Just as video game levels leave players wondering what will come next, AI can leave certain pieces of information or questions unresolved, creating a sense of anticipation that drives the user to move forward in order to discover the outcome. This cliffhanger effect (in Italian, *colpo di scena*) stimulates curiosity and encourages continued interaction with the content learned up to that point.

Role-Playing Games and Artificial Intelligence

Even though they can be “classified” among the forms of *aggiornamento/gamification*, role-playing games display certain specific features and potential that deserve to be considered separately. They are among the most stimulating ways to integrate AI and AI agents into learning. In short, the idea is to assign, within a conversation with a chatbot, different identities both to the AI and to its human interlocutor, so they can interact in realistic scenarios. These games not only encourage active participation, but also make it possible to exercise critical thinking, problem-solving skills, and memory through dialogue and direct experience.

In this exchange of information, the student needs to be very clear about one concept: they are not the only one assuming the role of “learner.” In the conversation, the “learning” function is present on both sides: the “machine” also learns from the relationship, that is, from the questions and reflections coming from the human. The issue is not limited to machine learning in the usual sense, but to machine learning that is immediately “reapplied” within the same conversation. Modern chatbots, especially those based on large language models (LLMs), use machine learning to

retain and reuse the results of previous interactions within the same dialogue. This is essential for creating a smooth and coherent conversational experience.

For this reason too, it is very important to learn how to question chatbots and/or AI agents: from the way we ask questions, the AI in turn “learns” and becomes increasingly capable of “hitting the mark” with its answers. By way of example—and in order to make as concrete as possible just how flexible and “extendable” this technology becomes when used through role-playing games—I will propose several examples of pairs of roles and how they can be used profitably (that is, played, enacted) in learning specific subjects. It will become clear that many of these “pairs” of role-players are, or can be, at the logical foundation of many AI agents as well.

Teacher–Student. One of the most straightforward role-playing games consists in assigning the AI the role of teacher, who questions the student on a particular topic. The student, in turn, plays the role of the one being examined, answering questions and receiving immediate feedback. Example: the student needs to review a history topic such as the French Revolution. The AI asks questions of increasing difficulty, corrects any errors, and provides targeted elaborations based on the student’s answers.

Tutor–Student. A variant of the “teacher–student” role-play is the tutoring scenario. If we want to draw a purely functional distinction here, we might say that the tutor does not necessarily have to give answers to the student, but rather helps the student find them independently, indicating a path or direction without necessarily laying out every step or every answer. The choice to adopt the “teacher” format or the “tutor” format depends on the goals and on the operational modalities with which one intends to interact with the AI.

Doctor–Patient. In the context of the biological and health sciences, AI can simulate the role of a patient with certain symptoms, while the

student (for instance, a university student in a health sciences, medicine, or pharmacy program) plays the doctor, who must diagnose the condition and propose a treatment. Example: the AI reports symptoms such as fever and joint pain. The student, drawing on their knowledge, must ask questions to gather further information, formulate a diagnosis (e.g., influenza), and suggest an appropriate therapy.

Interviewer–Interviewee. This is an excellent format for many different disciplines. In the interview game, the AI and the student simulate a debate or a journalistic-style interview. Example 1 (History): the student plays a journalist interviewing Napoleon Bonaparte (simulated by the AI) to explore the military and political strategies of the time. Example 2 (Philosophy): the AI plays Aristotle and answers the student’s questions about ethics and knowledge, encouraging them to formulate hypotheses and critical reflections.

Professional Simulations and Real-World Contexts. Beyond the examples mentioned above, there are many other applications of role-playing with AI. Lawyer and client: the student plays the lawyer and must advise the client (the AI) on a legal issue. Expert scientist and young researcher: the AI proposes scientific experiments and the student must hypothesize results and explanations. Political debate: the AI simulates a politician from a past or present era and the student must debate political and economic issues. Time traveler: the AI plays a historical figure with whom the student interacts in order to better understand the context of the period.

A Historical–Literary Comparison. To give a literary example, I am reminded of Niccolò Machiavelli’s letter to Francesco Vettori, where Machiavelli describes the end of his day: «Venuta la sera, mi ritorno a casa ed entro nel mio scrittoio; e in sull'uscio mi spoglio quella veste cotidiana, piena di fango e di loto, e mi metto panni reali e curiali; e rivestito condecientemente, entro nelle antiche corti delli antichi huomini, dove, da loro ricevuto amorevolmente, mi pasco di quel cibo

che solum è mio e ch'io nacqui per lui; dove io non mi vergogno parlare con loro e domandarli della ragione delle loro azioni; e quelli per loro humanità mi rispondono; e non sento per quattro hore di tempo alcuna noia, sdimentico ogni affanno, non temo la povertà, non mi sbigottisce la morte: tutto mi transferisco in loro.» I have quoted this passage because I would like to propose a small thought experiment. Let us reread it in light of the considerations above on the use of AI in role-playing games: the imaginative effort and play that Machiavelli describes can now be easily “replicated” by any of us with a modern chatbot or with agents of the type (to invent a few) “Learn the Divine Comedy with Dante,” “Ask Descartes who you are,” “Talk to Leopardi and you will no longer be melancholy,” and so on. Put another way: artificial intelligence makes it possible even for the most inexperienced teenager to carry out the kind of thought experiment Machiavelli describes in his letter to Vettori. Machiavelli’s example—and the possible dedicated applications, as well as AI agents of the “Talk to ...” type—highlights one of the strengths of artificial intelligence that other technological tools do not possess, or at least not to the same degree: adaptability. Indeed, extending the concept, *aggiornamento* applied to AI shows just how far it has already become the best educational tool we have in terms of flexibility and its ability to adapt to the student.

AI and Procedural Thinking.

In recent decades, persistent criticism from certain strands of pedagogy toward rote memorization has led students to a gradual loss of the ability to “proceduralize” knowledge. Yet—on the contrary—internalizing certain kinds of knowledge to the point of making them automatic is essential for effective study. Some subjects, such as foreign language learning and mathematics, specifically require this kind of automatization.

For example, speaking a foreign language fluently implies having internalized sentence structures that make it possible to express ideas

while focusing on meaning, instead of constantly having to rework the grammar. In mathematics, the automatization of multiplication tables is essential: without it, performing more complex calculations becomes nearly impossible.

The key principle of school learning that I want to highlight here can be summarized as follows: the more declarative knowledge is automatized, the freer the mind becomes to assimilate new information, making thinking both more fluid and more precise. While it is true that not every aspect of thinking can or should be proceduralized, it is undeniable that the trend toward superficiality in studying, which has become widespread in recent decades, has hindered the development of this valuable ability.

In this context, artificial intelligence can play a decisive role. AI can support students in memorizing and automatizing those types of knowledge that benefit most from proceduralization, offering a flexible and non-repetitive approach. In this way, the appropriate use of AI helps strengthen procedural thinking, making studying more effective and freeing up energy and “mental space” for acquiring new declarative knowledge (information).

Put differently: once certain fundamental notions have been automatized and proceduralized, the mind gains a significant saving of mental resources; a stored procedure frees the mind from having to recall every single step. We must therefore ask ourselves what kind of help AI can provide in this regard.

How Artificial Intelligence Can Guide and Shape Natural Procedural Thinking

By its very nature, procedural thinking can seem tedious and demand considerable effort to internalize. Yet this ability—essential for automating knowledge and making study more efficient—can be significantly strengthened precisely through the use of artificial intelligence. In addition, AI has the ability to vary content while still conveying it through recurring structures (for example, many

algebra exercises, although different from one another, require the same logical and mathematical procedures), and this variation in content transforms repetitive learning into a dynamic and engaging experience.

This can happen in several ways. We have already alluded to some of them when discussing, more generally, the didactic approach to AI through *aggiocamento*, but I now intend to focus on them specifically in relation to procedural learning. I am referring mainly to three processes: (A) intelligent repetition of procedures, (B) automatization of problem-solving strategies, and (C) progressive practice and immediate feedback.

(A) *Intelligent repetition of procedures* works much like a video game, when AI presents exercises and activities again and again, each time introducing new variations. This approach encourages the student to recognize patterns and to improve the speed and effectiveness of their responses, gradually consolidating the procedures they have learned.

(B) *The automatization of strategies*—even before the procedures of resolution themselves—also works in a way similar to video games. Just as a gamer learns to memorize winning combinations and moves, the student is guided by AI in identifying the best strategies for solving complex problems: whether it is performing calculations or algebraic manipulations, answering history questions, or analyzing a text, the process becomes increasingly fluid and natural. In this case, automatizing the strategy is a necessary precondition for automatizing the procedure and, in fact, helps us better understand the procedure itself. Learning in terms of strategies rather than isolated bits of information encourages thinking in terms of patterns, networks of knowledge, and contexts rather than disconnected details. As happens in video games, where it is not necessary to remember every single element but rather to learn effective behavioral patterns, the student learns to use strategic thinking to approach and solve problems,

thereby fostering a deeper and more functional understanding.

(C) With *progressive practice*, AI can gradually calibrate the level of difficulty, just as in video games where the final levels (those in which one faces a “boss”) represent a growing challenge. In this way, the student tackles increasingly demanding tasks, consolidating their knowledge and progressively developing mastery of the content, in parallel with the stabilization in their mind of the structures and procedures that make their thinking more fluid.

Finally, as for immediate and adaptive feedback, in the world of games a mistake does not mean the game is over; it represents an opportunity to try again and improve. AI adopts the same approach: it provides immediate feedback and corrective suggestions, allowing the student to refine the procedure until it becomes virtually error-free.

Adding study routines

The considerations put forward so far make sense above all in light of a fact that it is pointless to dance around and that must instead be acknowledged with complete intellectual honesty: the use of artificial intelligences has become, in just a few years, too advantageous to ignore—especially in the production of texts: reports, essays, emails, even school papers and university theses. In a few seconds we can obtain coherent, well-structured texts, often even elegant. The point is that this ease is not neutral: it is profoundly changing the nature of the mental effort required of human beings. And let’s be clear: this is not a problem limited to unmotivated students. It concerns everyone.

If for centuries the main effort was to create and articulate meanings—that is, to produce texts, arguments, problems, and solutions—today the effort is increasingly shifting toward another activity: checking, selecting, judging the texts that AI generates. The work is no longer so much the retrieval and creation of information as its recognition.^{iv}

This transformation is a double-edged sword. On the one hand, it leads to a superficialization of knowledge: we become good at quickly recognizing “right” concepts and phrases, but less accustomed to actually constructing them from our internal resources. On the other hand, however, there is an enormous expansion—even if often a superficial one—of our informational horizon: we can explore domains far removed from our training, jump from one field of knowledge to another in a few clicks, always having in front of us an “overview” of what we need.

The psycho-cognitive difference between merely recognizing a piece of content and being able to produce it actively is profound, and it decisively shapes the quality of learning. If we restrict the discussion to information and factual knowledge, we must distinguish with precision between (a) recognizing an item of information when it is present in the environment—for example in a text, an exercise, or an already-formulated answer—and (b) being able to retrieve it from memory in the absence of cues, reorganize it, describe it, and, in more complex cases, rework it creatively within a coherent conceptual framework. Even simple retrieval from memory constitutes a qualitative leap beyond recognition: the difference between the two is not merely one of degree, but often one of kind, because the cognitive processes involved change, as does the attentional and focusing effort required, and—above all—the stability of the knowledge that results.

A familiar analogy makes this distinction immediately intelligible. It is one thing to recognize a banknote when it is in front of you—identifying colors, size, graphic elements, and its denomination—and quite another to describe it accurately in its absence, recalling its distinctive features and organizing them into a sufficiently precise verbal representation. In the first case, the environment provides most of the necessary information: the cognitive system primarily has to “hook” perceptual patterns to labels already stored. In the second, by contrast, the information

must be generated internally: semantic memory must be activated, relevant details selected, ordered, and translated into a controlled expressive form.

This difference is not a minor theoretical point: it touches the very core of school-based and professional knowledge. A form of knowing that were limited to recognition would, by its nature, remain dependent on the outside world: it would allow one to identify what others have already produced, but it would not guarantee the ability to act, argue, and decide autonomously. In educational contexts, in fact, recognition often amounts to “following” a meaning that someone else has already constructed; knowing in the full sense, by contrast, implies being able to retrieve and use that meaning independently of its presence in the immediate context, until it can be transformed into performance: explaining, demonstrating, solving, applying, transferring to new situations.

It is precisely at this point that one of the most recurrent instructional problems in secondary school becomes visible. Not infrequently, unmotivated or insufficiently encouraged students, when faced with a topic, declare: “But I already know this.” That claim, however, is often a symptom of a cognitive misunderstanding: what is being mistaken for knowledge is, more often, familiarity. “It sounds familiar” means that the content triggers a feeling of recognition; but familiarity does not coincide with possession of usable knowledge. One can recognize a concept without being able to define it; one can identify the correct formula without being able to derive it or apply it; one can “know” an answer in the sense of selecting it among options already provided, without being able to produce it autonomously. Educationally, the difference is crucial, because familiarity tends to generate an illusion of competence that blocks effort and reduces the willingness to take responsibility for one’s own study.

It follows that genuinely effective instruction cannot be satisfied with training recognition, nor can it be reduced to practices that foster super-

ficial learning through cues, hints, or excessive facilitation. On the contrary, it should systematically aim at free retrieval of information from semantic memory and at the active production of meaning: explanations in one's own words, scheduled recall, arguments without external scaffolding, applications in varied contexts, reconstruction tasks, and forms of assessment that require not the mere presence of traces, but their actual availability. In other words, the goal is not cognitive “copy-and-paste”—the repetition or selection of ready-made content—but the autonomous construction and reconstruction of conceptual structures.

It is obvious that such an orientation runs up against a natural tendency of the cognitive system: the drive to minimize energy expenditure. The brain, constantly engaged in maintaining vital functions and managing attention, favors cognitive shortcuts whenever they are available; recognition, compared to retrieval and re-elaboration, is often an efficient and rewarding shortcut. Yet precisely because it is “easy,” it risks producing fragile knowledge: an apparent competence that works as long as the information is present or suggested, but collapses when operational autonomy is required.

From this standpoint, the age of artificial intelligence makes the issue even more pressing. Immediate access to well-formed texts and plausible answers can reinforce the habit of passive recognition: understanding is confused with mere exposure, and competence with the ability to select among prepackaged options. But if we want to “keep pace” with a cultural and technological context that is accelerating rapidly, it becomes indispensable to strengthen precisely what automation cannot deliver as a substitute: a well-organized internal memory, the capacity to retrieve and integrate knowledge, and the ability to generate new meanings in a controlled and responsible way. Ultimately, education cannot limit itself to training recognition: it must form subjects capable of producing knowledge, because it is only in production—in autonomous retrieval, reflective use, and re-

elaboration—that knowledge becomes truly our own.

To better understand this transformation, we can use a metaphor. Imagine our mind as a swimming pool full of water, where the water represents our knowledge. Up to now, let's say, this pool has been 10 meters wide, 25 meters long, and 3 meters deep: 750 cubic meters of water. With the arrival of AI, the pool has expanded horizontally: suppose it is now 30 meters by 25, but only 1 meter deep. The total water is still 750 cubic meters, but distributed differently. That means we can “get around” more easily, move across a much wider surface of interests and topics—but swimming in it is harder. It becomes dangerous to dive in expecting depth: you risk slamming into the bottom.

The more we widen the pool horizontally, the more we are forced to lower its depth—at least if we do not increase the amount of water, that is, if we do not invest time and effort to truly deepen our understanding. The risk, if we continue down this road without corrective measures, is that we will end up with a huge pool so shallow that it becomes impossible to swim in: we can only walk through ankle-deep water, deluding ourselves that we “know” because we recognize the names of things, without ever truly immersing ourselves in their meaning.

This is where the crucial theme of authentic learning comes into play. Real improvement is not achieved simply by exposing ourselves to more information—that is easy now; AI gives it to us at almost zero cost—but by introducing more effective routines of study and mental processing. In other words, it is not enough to have more content: we need new cognitive habits, more solid ones and, inevitably, more demanding ones.

Acquiring new study habits is one of the hardest things we can ask of a student. It means changing how time is managed, how notes are taken, how review is done, how we check what has actually been understood. Above all, it means moving from the illusion of understanding—because something “sounds familiar”—to the ability

to recall concepts, arguments, definitions without external supports. And it is precisely on this point that AI, paradoxically, can become an ally rather than an enemy of deep learning. The problem—worth repeating to the point of exhaustion—is not the tool in itself, but how it is used. If AI is used only to generate texts in our place, it pushes us toward the wide and shallow pool. But if we use it to introduce and maintain new study routines, it can help us make the water deeper and learn to swim better.

Think of the classroom situation: a single teacher must manage many students, each with their own specific difficulties, their own pace, their own weaknesses and strengths. It is materially impossible to offer every student continuous, personalized tutoring. Here AI can play the role of a medium, a tool interposed between student and teacher. The student, alone or together with the teacher, can use AI support to plan a personalized study routine: define study times, identify gaps to fill, choose the topics to address more insistently.

Once this routine has been set up—a kind of cognitive “training plan”—it can be brought to the teacher’s attention, since the teacher knows the student as a whole: they have seen the student’s path, they sense their fragilities, they know their potential. At this point the teacher intervenes as a “meta-tutor”: no longer only the one who explains content, but the one who supervises and improves how the student studies, correcting the routine prepared with AI and adapting it to the concrete person in front of them.

This shift in perspective is fundamental, because it begins with a key awareness: there are no shortcuts. Changing a study habit is as difficult as changing an eating or exercise habit. It requires time, consistency, small daily adjustments. And often the school system, as it is organized, does not help: schedules are packed, curricula tight, time for explanation limited. Many teachers, even with the best intentions, are forced to give a quick “overview” of a topic and then move on, without being able to return to the same issues again and

again—reiterating them, expanding them, deepening them, connecting them to each other—as would be necessary to truly consolidate learning.

The result is that students learn to recognize many things—terms, formulas, dates, definitions—but struggle to recall them independently. In the language of cognitive science, the difference is crucial: recognition is easy but superficial; recall (retrieval) is more demanding, but it is the only form of knowledge we can truly use when we think, reason, discuss, create something new. When we limit ourselves to recognition, it is as if we are moving around in the shallow pool: we see everything, but we cannot immerse ourselves. When we are able to recall, by contrast, we can “push off from the edge” and swim in depth.

Ideally, the teacher should work every day—and day after day—on the foundational questions, returning and returning to the key conceptual cores, progressively adding new details, linking what was studied yesterday to what is being addressed today. It is this work of intelligent (selective and targeted) repetition, of gradual expansion, that allows students to assimilate deeply instead of merely recognizing superficially. But to do this takes time, energy, and supporting tools.

And here artificial intelligence can come back into play, in a virtuous way. Adding AI-managed study routines means building an ally that does not get tired and can follow each student’s individual rhythm. This is not about assigning AI “the job of thinking for us,” but about using it as a “personal trainer,” as an organizational machine that helps us put into practice those good practices that we have also explained here, in this study, and that we know are effective but struggle to maintain on our own: scheduled retrieval, open-ended quizzes, explanations in our own words, alternating recognition and production exercises, time management, small comprehension checks. It is not merely delegating to AI the organization of a student’s studying; it is using an advanced technological instrument to hold together, in one sweep, the entire body of knowledge the student must

face, the student's own strengths and critical points—and to do so, necessarily, with the support at least of the teacher and of other professional figures when needed (educators, psychologists, speech therapists, etc.).

In short, a study routine with AI can come about like this: the student questions the chatbot, providing as many relevant elements as possible: what grade they are in, how they evaluate themselves and how they are evaluated by teachers (trying to be as objective as possible). They indicate the subject to study, the specific topics they must learn, their perceived gaps, and the time they have available each day or each week. They can also specify the format of the assessment awaiting them: an oral exam, a written test, a university exam. Starting from this information, they ask the chatbot to draft a program, a training plan of formative activities to carry out in student–AI interaction.

This program is not an abstract list of things to do, but a real pathway: retrieval exercises, simulated oral examinations, guided questioning, guided explanations, periodic reminders spaced across days, suggestions for taking notes more effectively. The student does not stop thinking—quite the opposite: they are continually called upon to produce answers, explanations, examples, and to confront their own errors. Once this routine has been created, the student submits it to the teacher. Here technology meets the educational relationship. The teacher, knowing the history and characteristics of the person in front of them, can modify the program, adjust its pace, introduce moments of discussion in class (or separately with the individual student) that connect with the activities carried out with AI. In this framework, the teacher truly becomes a meta-tutor: not only explaining the discipline, but guiding the student in the art of studying, using AI as a lever to personalize the path. Thus, instead of settling for a pool that is wider and shallower, we can use AI to redistribute the water: to deepen certain key points, to learn to

dive where it truly matters, to build the ability to swim independently.

Why it's important to follow routines with AI's help.

There really are many study methods and numerous effective memorization techniques—we know that by now: books, courses, videos, and lectures explain how to take better notes, how to use concept maps, how to do spaced repetition, how to make every minute spent with books more productive. As the author always repeats, not all methods and study strategies work well all the time; in fact, the opposite is often true. But there is always something that can be done in any situation, and yet it is difficult to get most people to change even minimal study habits. Those who teach these tools regularly observe a recurring paradox: people who want to improve the way they study are, in most cases, sincerely motivated. They listen carefully, recognize the value of the advice they receive, and often get excited by the prospect of becoming more effective and less stressed. At the outset, there is no lack of goodwill. And yet, after a few days or a few weeks, something very human almost always happens: old habits come back to reclaim their place, the painstakingly sketched-out study method is abandoned, and people return to the usual mode—the one that may not work very well, but is at least known, familiar, comfortable in its inefficiency.

To understand why this happens, it helps to recall a point that echoes in the reflections of Alan Baddeley and many other scholars of memory: memory gives you nothing for free; it gives back what you have given it. This is not a catchy slogan, but a realistic description of how we learn: what is not practiced, revisited, reworked, connected to something else simply dissolves, or else remains in a form so fragile that it cannot be used when it is needed. As a result, introducing a new study method does not mean merely changing a few technical details; it entails an initial investment of energy, attention, and time. At first, using

a new strategy is more costly than continuing to do what we have always done, because studying differently means, in practice, acquiring a new habit. And acquiring a new mental habit is as demanding as changing the way we walk or our posture when we sit: the body tends to fall back into its habitual pattern, even if that pattern is not the healthiest.

It is precisely at this moment—in the initial phase, when applying the new method requires more effort—that most people give in. Not because the method does not work (even though, it must be emphasized, not everything works for everyone and that knowing how to choose and evaluate is a skill which, when missing in the educator, makes things worse by wrongly blaming the method when the mistake lies in having applied it to the wrong situation),^v but because it is not given time to work. The brain protests in a silent but effective way: “With the old system you were faster—wouldn’t it make sense to keep going like that?” Faced with this resistance, almost invisible but extremely powerful, people return to the old way of studying—the one that produces poor or inconsistent results, but does not demand the effort of reorganizing the way one learns. The problem, then, is not the scarcity of available techniques, but the difficulty of transforming a potentially good method into a stable routine, embedded in everyday life.

This is where routines built with the help of artificial intelligence could take on a decisive role. Not because AI possesses any magic over memory, but because it can become a constant support precisely at the most critical point: the transition from “I know what I should do” to “I actually do it, every day, until it becomes natural.” Only by changing one’s study routines, in fact, can one truly change one’s habits; and only by changing habits, in the long run, can ineffective study methods be replaced by more high-performing approaches. Routines are the bridge between the level of intentions and the level of actual behavior.

In this scenario, artificial intelligence can function as a kind of coach (and meta-coach) and as a discreet but always-available manager: it helps schedule study sessions, reminds you when it is time to review, proposes retrieval exercises instead of limiting you to passive repetition, varies activities so as to keep attention alive. It can track progress, point out relapses into old habits, suggest small daily adjustments. Instead of relying only on willpower—a precious but limited resource—the student can lean on an external structure that regularly reminds them of the new way of doing things. It is a support that does not eliminate effort, but makes it more manageable, distributed over time, channeled into a concrete form.

In this sense, AI should not be seen as a surrogate for human memory or intelligence, but as a device to help people do what, on their own, they find extremely difficult: maintain a new style of learning over time, resist the temptation to return to the old method, organize their days in a way that is consistent with the goals they claim to want to achieve. The study techniques exist; we know the principles of good memorization; the scientific evidence for what works is not lacking. The real sore point is the distance between “I know” and “I do.” AI-supported study routines can help reduce precisely that distance, helping students turn the desire to change into a real, everyday change, made of small repeated actions, until the new methods become an integral part of how they learn. Only then will memory—faithful to its nature—begin truly to give back what it has been given consistently: no longer just pages flipped through in a hurry, but stable, organized, usable knowledge.

Routines, Attention, and Metacognition

Study routines are not a quirky habit of “disciplined” people: they are a practical way to conserve attention. When you repeat more or less the same steps (setting up the desk, always opening the same notebook or file, setting a timer, deciding in advance what you will do in the next 25–40

minutes, taking notes in a particular way, underlining according to a certain criterion, repeating a lesson “x times,” and so on), you are shifting part of the work from “thinking” to “recognizing.” If, in the previous pages, I argued that shifting (and reducing) cognitive effort from “creating thought” and “retrieving memories” to the recognition of those contents in something external (a book, a file on the computer, the teacher’s very voice as they explain, etc.) is problematic, here I am now suggesting we do the exact opposite. Why? Because when it comes to operations with a low conceptual and creative-ideational load, but which involve standardized (or standardizable) processes and procedures, it is appropriate—indeed advisable—to save precious cognitive energy.

You save energy where it makes sense to do so precisely in order to devote the attention thus “accumulated” to something more important. The mind no longer has to renegotiate, each time, the beginning of a study session. By establishing routines wherever possible, the mind gets up to speed with less friction. This is a decisive point, because attention is not a spotlight you can keep turned on at will: it is an unstable balance among mental energy, active goals, and competing stimuli. A routine, in essence, reduces the number of preliminary decisions and lowers background noise. As a result, sustaining concentration for longer becomes more likely. Moreover, having a “path”—at least structurally speaking (that is, a way of “doing things”)—already laid out, and one that remains valid even as the nature of the things themselves changes (the subjects and topics to be studied vary from time to time), means that along the way attention encounters fewer stimuli to latch onto in order to wander—and thus fewer opportunities to get distracted.

This idea—making likely what, left to itself, is fragile—is also the guiding thread when artificial intelligence enters the study process, especially in the form of chatbots. A chatbot, as should by now be clear, is not merely a “book that answers”: it is an interlocutor that lives on the same

device that hosts notifications, links, and the temptation to keep jumping endlessly from one topic to another. It is therefore an extraordinarily powerful attentional object. It can be a formidable ally for staying focused, or an accelerator of dispersion. And the difference, almost always, lies in the quality of the routines through which you use it.

The topic of cognitive attention in relation to AI is complex and cannot be addressed here even in outline; only a few brief cues can be offered. One of them is to think of attention as a resource manager rather than an act of “willpower.” In cognitive terms, attention resembles a priority-management system. Simplifying: you have a goal (understand a theorem, summarize a chapter, prepare a presentation), you have a limited working memory (a few elements at a time, fragile, easily disrupted), and you have a constellation of stimuli trying to “get in” (thoughts, sounds, sudden curiosities, performance anxiety, notifications). Concentration means keeping the goal active and protecting working memory from unnecessary intrusions. Here a frequently underestimated concept comes in: the cost of context switching. Every time you move from the book to the chatbot, from the chatbot to the browser, from the browser to a video, you are not just “switching windows.” You are asking the brain to: (1) suspend one set of information; (2) load another; (3) remember where you left off; (4) reconstruct a sense of direction. This process is costly, and you pay for it in two currencies: time and quality. Time, because you lose minutes in micro-reconstructions; quality, because part of working memory is occupied with “holding together” the transition, instead of the content you are trying to understand. In addition, once you have moved into the new context, some notions from the previous one remain in memory, fatiguing working memory and constituting a possible source of disturbance and/or noise.

Routines serve precisely to reduce these costs: they decide in advance when you will interact with AI, for what purpose, and in what form, so that attention does not have to continually rede-

fine the task. At this point the real enemy emerges: not distraction, but indeterminacy. If routines make it easier to start and to remain in the work, AI can make it easier to stay on the right point and to verify what you truly know—provided you avoid the most common paradox: using AI to reduce all effort, and then discovering that together with the effort you have also reduced learning.

Cognitive overload.^{vi} Without an appropriate and carefully evaluated study routine, not only do you risk giving too much weight to recognition and too little to the creation of meanings and the retrieval of knowledge from long-term memory; all of this can be induced and/or aggravated precisely by putting “too much on the fire,” so that one “perceives” a great deal of knowledge and processes very little of it. The critical point, when studying with chatbots, is that their “informational generosity” can become toxic. A chatbot, if not guided, tends to maximize completeness and coverage: definitions, exceptions, examples, variants, historical deepening, lateral connections, methodological notes. The result is often a well-written text, but cognitively unmanageable. Here the problem of cognitive load comes to the fore: instead of facilitating study, AI can produce an overload that fractures attention, prevents deep understanding, and induces a feeling of “conceptual drowning.”

The reason is simple and, in a sense, relentless: the human mind does not work like a hard drive that accumulates; it works like a small workbench. As has already been said, working memory—the platform on which you temporarily hold concepts, steps, and relations while you reason—has limited capacity. If too many pieces arrive on the bench at once, even if all are useful “in absolute terms,” you can no longer assemble them. And when you cannot assemble them, three typical things happen: (1) you lose the thread and start rereading without truly integrating; (2) you jump from one point to another looking for handholds, further increasing the chaos; (3) you rely on the illusion of having understood because it “sounds

clear,” but the mental structure has not actually formed.

The indeterminate formulation of the goal. With chatbots this risk is amplified by a decisive detail: the model does not spontaneously know your threshold at that moment. If you ask, “Explain photosynthesis” or “Summarize Kant,” the request is too broad, and the chatbot, in order to be helpful, broadens even more. The error often arises before the answer: it arises in the indeterminate formulation of the goal. When the goal is vague, the answer tends to be encyclopedic; when the answer is encyclopedic, cognitive load increases; when the load increases, attention collapses or fragments. For this reason, in AI-assisted studying, a key skill is not “asking questions,” but designing information: requesting that content be provided in a sequenced, hierarchical form, with gradually increasing difficulty. In practice, this means imposing on AI the same discipline that a good teacher applies in class: first the skeleton, then the details; first the necessary concepts, then the exceptions; first a guiding example, then exercises; first the basic level, then the advanced level.

In study—whether at school or self-directed—concentration does not arise from perfect silence or heroic motivation. It arises from a repeatable sequence of gestures and decisions that protect the goal in mind, limit context switching, and turn interaction with the chatbot into training: less consumption of answers, more production, more retrieval, more targeted correction. Within that framework, AI stops being a conversational vortex and becomes what it can be at its best: a tireless tutor who, instead of taking you by the hand all the way to the solution, continually brings you back to the most important question for attention: “What exactly are you trying to do right now?” This return to oneself, in order to cultivate deep self-awareness, leads us to the final topic of this essay: metacognition.

Metacognition

Metacognition in school learning does not coincide with what a student knows, nor with any single technique they apply, but with the ability to step back from oneself—to observe from above what one is doing while one is doing it. It is a step back, but not a retreat; it is the minimal distance that allows the mind not merely to be “caught” by the task, but to govern it. When this distance stabilizes, studying stops being a sequence of more-or-less lucky attempts and becomes a process the student can direct, correct, make more efficient, and, above all, understand. In this sense, metacognition is not an ornament of intelligence, but a condition of its growth: it is what transforms learning into conscious learning.

Reflecting on what one is learning and on how one is learning it means recognizing that learning is not a single act, but a complex dynamic, made of choices, checks, revisions, sometimes misunderstandings and repairs. The heart of this dynamic, in school, often lies at the delicate junction between working memory and long-term memory. Working memory is the desk on which the mind holds, for a few moments, the pieces of the problem: the data in an exercise, the sentences of a text, the conditions of an assignment, the steps of a line of reasoning. It is a precious surface, but a limited one, easily overloaded.

I often use this example to illustrate the nature of working memory, a construct that, surprisingly, is defined rather unclearly even in the most authoritative psychology textbooks. To grasp the function of this system, just think about the act of conversing: for my speech to be fluent and coherent, I must keep three temporal dimensions active at the same time. I have to retain the trace of what I have just said, monitor what I am saying in the present, and plan what I intend to say in the next instant. In parallel, it is necessary to keep the overall schema of the argument accessible; without this capacity for simultaneous integration, it would be impossible to articulate complex discourse or to express a complete thought.^{vii}

Long-term memory, by contrast, is the stable repository of concepts, procedures, images, examples, “traces” that can be retrieved and reused. Effective learning happens when the student manages intelligently the transit between these two dimensions: selecting what must remain active, connecting it to what they already know, deciding whether they are truly understanding or merely following an apparent rhythm.

Metacognition is the device that oversees this transit, because it introduces a question that, at school, is as simple as it is decisive: “What is happening in my mind while I study?” Here we touch a point that is often overlooked: the plasticity of learning depends not only on having cognitive strategies, but on the ability to make them an object of attention—to compare them, modify them, adapt them to the context. It is not enough to “use” a strategy; one must be able to “manipulate” it and, if necessary, change it. The difference is like the difference between driving a car by instinct and also knowing how to diagnose an engine problem, recognize when you are burning too much fuel, choose a more effective route.

Metacognition^{viii} does exactly this: it turns one’s way of studying into a mental object that can be manipulated, described, discussed. And that is why, at its core, it is not an automatic process: it involves consciousness, intentionality, language. The mind has to narrate to itself what it is doing, even if only through an essential inner dialogue, because without language the observation of one’s own thinking remains confused, hazy, hard to sustain. And here, even with the strategies, processes, and dynamics described in the previous pages, the use of AI can play a central role. Metacognition, self-awareness—which, as Peruzzi rightly observes, although closely connected, are not the same thing—the role of the teacher, artificial intelligence: these are all elements that integrate into learning to intervene actively in the acquisition of information, avoiding indiscriminate collection; in selection, distinguishing what is central from what is accessory; in organization, in the sequences and

hierarchies of information; in evaluation, that is, in the delicate act of establishing whether what one has done “works,” whether it can stand up to a test, whether it can be transferred elsewhere. Along this trajectory, the student is not invited to become more “skilled” in some generic sense, but more precise in diagnosing their own functioning. It is a form of lucidity: not a detached coldness, but the capacity (to be increased as the years pass and the individual matures) to recognize the exact point where understanding is present and the point where it is missing.

This is where another crucial idea belongs: in order to self-regulate, one must be able to objectify oneself. Conscious self-regulation is, in a sense, a continuous internal negotiation: I establish a goal, choose a method, monitor progress, intervene when progress is not good. But this cycle cannot begin if the student cannot identify, with at least minimal accuracy, their own cognitive states. The original metacognitive question is brutal in its simplicity: “Do I understand this or do I not understand it?” And yet, precisely because it is simple, it is also often avoided: many students (and, unfortunately, I must add, many programs/curricula/ministry guidelines, etc.) confuse familiarity with understanding, recognition with mastery (closely tied to the voluntary retrieval of information from the “warehouse” of semantic memory), the smoothness of reading with having built a stable mental model.

Metacognition is crucial because, beyond awareness, it stimulates and introduces criteria, signals, indicators. It is the art of recognizing when an idea is truly “mine,” when I can explain it, apply it, transform it—and when, instead, it is still an opaque object I am carrying without grasping.

When students really practice reflecting on how they learn, something subtle but transformative happens: they gradually stop identifying with their habits and begin to consider them as choices. It is a psychologically powerful shift, and it goes hand in hand with the conscious use of different

routines of thought and action. If I think, “That’s just how I am, I don’t understand math,” my identity absorbs the failure and makes it untouchable. If instead I learn to say, “In this kind of problem I tend to skip the final check,” I have transformed a supposed sentence into a modifiable behavior. This shifts responsibility, but in a liberating sense: it is not blame, it is the possibility of intervention. The student becomes the actor of their own development, not the spectator of their outcomes.

When this “mental posture” takes root, the relationship with questions and answers changes as well. School often trains students to answer quickly, to close out an assignment rapidly, to turn in a product ... and here too we can notice many of the failures and misunderstandings in the use of artificial intelligence and in the evaluation of students’ preparation; AI that, if used well, can instead produce effective, robust, durable results but, necessarily, results that can be evaluated more objectively over the long term precisely because it interacts with metacognition. It is metacognition, in fact, that “educates”—if cultivated day by day and therefore over the long term—to care for the quality of an answer: not only “what do I have to write,” but “what am I doing when I write,” “what criterion am I using,” “why does this solution seem correct to me,” “what alternatives have I excluded and for what reason.” It is a maturation that can be recognized in how the student argues, checks, self-corrects. And the more this care grows, the more autonomy and resilience grow: error becomes useful information, not a final judgment.

In this framework, the arrival of Artificial Intelligence is not simply the addition of a powerful means, but the opening of new ways to make visible and manipulable what, until yesterday, remained implicit. Digital technology, for some time now, as Calvani reminds us, performs a kind of outward-turning function: it lightens the mind’s load by shifting outward calculations, memories, searches, archiving. This effect is real and often positive, because it frees up resources in working

memory and makes it possible to invest more attention in comprehension. However, in everyday and spontaneous use, this externalization risks stopping at the level of operational support: technology becomes a prosthesis that does things in our place, not a tool that helps us understand how we are reasoning. This is where active use of AI—especially interactive and simulation environments—can function as a mind tool, that is, as a tool capable not only of simplifying but of amplifying the cognitive and metacognitive dimension.

The decisive knot, once again, is objectification. If metacognition requires turning one's ways of thinking into objects of observation, then any technology that makes those ways more visible, comparable, and discussable becomes a natural ally. Many digital environments—and today, in particular, many AI-based applications—make it possible to “externalize” not only the problem but also the strategy. A step in a line of reasoning can be rewritten, broken down, represented, visualized; a decision can be justified, criticized, compared with an alternative. AI, if well guided, can propose variants, make assumptions explicit, show consequences, highlight typical errors or missing steps. Not because it “knows” in the student's place, but because it makes quicker and more accessible the comparison among different reasoning schemas, and therefore facilitates awareness of one's own mental habits.

A student who uses metacognition, acquired also through the “methodological” steps shown in the previous pages, could, for example, ask a chatbot not for the answer to a question, but for the reconstruction of the path—or better yet, of multiple different but convergent paths: “Show me two different strategies to get here and tell me what final checks I can do to verify correctness.” This kind of request—picking up another topic addressed earlier—shifts the axis of studying from product to process. The student is no longer looking for the shortcut, but for the atlas: they want to see the geography of possible routes. Or they might ask: “What is the most likely mistake a stu-

dent makes at this step?” and then check whether that mistake matches their own. In these cases, AI functions as an advanced mirror: it does not solve the effort in the learner's place, but makes clearer the point at which effort becomes instructive—the already mentioned *Desirable Difficulties*.

Another aspect of scaffolding also returns here, revealing all its importance precisely in relation to metacognition: simulation. Put simply: simulation is a concept that swings like a pendulum between play and scientific hypothesis, and it would be very interesting to show its forms and dynamics. But staying on topic, it is entirely evident that simulation is the “gym” that can make a student—at least potentially—a future scientist or, in any case, a future rational adult. Simulation is in fact experimentation carried out with imagination: testing ideas with fantasy, but with a fantasy that tries—or at least should—reckon with reality. And this is where metacognition slips in. Simulation environments (and AI can create very many of them, perhaps—in principle—even an infinity), and more generally well-designed cognitive “games,” can be described as a gym for consciousness. Simulation, when it is built to bring out choices and consequences, forces the student to “think about how they think,” because it is not enough to repeat a procedure: one must understand why a procedure works in one context and fails in another. A simulation makes visible what is normally hidden, because every action leaves a trace and every trace produces an observable effect. The student sees not only the final outcome, but the behavior of the system over time. This forces them to formulate hypotheses, test them, verify them, correct them. In other words, it pushes them to occupy exactly the metacognitive position: that of someone who directs and monitors their own learning.

There is also an often underestimated aspect: simulation and AI foster a dissociation between the thinking subject and their ways of thinking. In a traditional classroom, thinking often remains private; it emerges only in fragments,

through an answer, an assignment, an oral intervention. With interactive tools (and most of all AI), however, ways of reasoning can become shared objects of discussion: a strategy can be displayed on a screen, a chain of steps can be commented on, an error can be analyzed not as a personal label but as a property of a procedure. This changes the climate: thinking becomes laboratory material. And when thinking becomes laboratory material, error loses much of its emotional weight and gains diagnostic value.

AI use can support metacognition also on the evaluation side—not in the reductive sense of a grade, but in the richer sense of self-assessment and awareness of criteria. A teacher who designs a learning path can use AI tools to generate questions aimed not only at knowledge of content but at knowledge of processes. Questions such as “How did you learn this topic?”, “What method did you use to solve this problem?”, “At what point did you realize you didn’t understand and what did you do?”, “If you had to teach it to a classmate, where would you start?” are not mere curiosities: they are instructional devices that force the student to make their operational model explicit. Even when the student answers imperfectly, the very fact of having to take a position generates learning. It is as if the metacognitive question forces the mind to draw a map of itself.

In this process, AI can have a bidirectional role. On the one hand, it helps the student produce more articulated descriptions of their own procedure, suggesting categories, offering examples of reflection, proposing comparisons among strategies. On the other hand, it can increase the teacher’s methodological awareness, because it quickly provides a repertoire of different ways to question content, to build assessments, to identify criteria. The risk, of course, is to confuse the availability of tools with the quality of the design: no AI replaces educational intention. But when the intention is clear, AI can speed up planning and make it more refined, fostering that virtuous circle in which the teacher also becomes more explicitly

metacognitive: they do not merely “teach,” but reflect on how understanding is built in the classroom, on what choices facilitate it and what choices hinder it.

This possibility, however, requires an essential caution: using AI in a metacognitive way means not delegating judgment. The assistant can propose plausible but wrong answers; it can oversimplify; it can induce dependence; it can make speed seductive at the expense of depth. Precisely for this reason—especially with respect to metacognition—the most educational use of AI is not the one that offers solutions, but the one that trains criteria. In a mature school practice, AI can become a partner in critical training: a tool asked to justify, to make assumptions explicit, to indicate possible errors, and then verified through sources, examples, counterexamples. In this way, technology does not weaken metacognition: it provokes it. It forces the student to ask not only “What does the AI say?” but “Why should I believe it?”, “How can I check?”, “Which part do I really understand and which part am I only accepting?”

When you look at the overall picture, an important distinction emerges. Traditional tools mainly tend to lighten: they shift outside the mind the weight of certain operations. AI and simulations, instead—if placed within a precise instructional design—can also amplify: they make reflection more intense, reasoning more visible, strategy more controllable, process more discussable. In this sense, metacognition is not only compatible with advanced technology: it can find in it a privileged environment, because what is metacognitive often requires a surface of representation, a mirror, a comparison. AI can help transform metalinguistic consciousness into something tangible: a written dialogue, a sequence of steps, a map of alternatives, a log of attempts and corrections.

The final point, perhaps the most educational one, is that metacognition does not coincide with one technique among others, but with an education in cognitive freedom. When a student learns to thematize their ways of learning, they take pos-

session of a part of themselves that used to be automatic and therefore inaccessible. And when that part becomes accessible, it also becomes transformable. School, then, no longer limits itself to transmitting content: it teaches how to govern one's own learning through guidance—the teacher's guidance, which remains fundamental, especially for transmitting and eliciting metacognition in and among students.

Conclusions

In our domain of competence (school learning), AI, on the one hand, makes it easier to compose texts and to gather information in a coherent way; on the other hand, it imposes a careful and in-depth critical analysis of its outputs. For example, confirmation bias can entail significant risks. Even though AI is improving rapidly and the risk of errors decreases day by day, it is essential to remember that the information it produces must always be verified and vetted by human beings—checking its accuracy and assessing whether it is appropriate (to be included). The problem, then, is not only potential errors, but also—and often—omissions. Ending up taking what it produces as good (confirmation bias) is a serious mistake not only, nor so much, because of the errors AI still makes today (even though there are now filters that greatly reduce that possibility), but above all because it can generate a text that is biased, or flat, or—even worse—devoid of precisely the information that, if included, the user might find extremely significant. For a truly conscious use oriented toward learning, artificial intelligence not only does not make things easier; on the contrary, it requires additional work of critical analysis, integration, or, not infrequently, “pruning.”

Already today, AI applications designed specifically for studying are being developed (for example, Google Learn About), in which many of the study methods suggested in this work are being introduced, and it is easy to predict that there will be more and more of them in the future, increasingly targeted at solving specific problems.

In any case, whatever the technological developments may be, in education AI is producing content—written texts, audio, or audio-video—that is increasingly precise in relation to our goals and our current competencies.

However, it is we who must learn from informational materials, and the work of revision and deepening that once applied to paper texts is neither—nor can it be—avoided: it evolves, becoming ever more specialized and adapted to the specific needs of each user. The AI battle will be won by those humans who learn to use it better and better, and that will mean that, to use it better, we human beings will need more knowledge and skills, not less.

As Alberto Peruzzi points out at the end of his book *Molto rumore per qualcosa* (Metilene, 2024), we should not even speak of artificial intelligence as if it were a single thing, because it is not: like natural intelligence (in the human species and in others), AI is also a multitude of systems (p. 206). It follows that «as regards both the advantages we derive from these applications and the risks they present, we cannot lump everything together. [...] The attention devoted—only in recent times—by the media to AI has not helped people recognize this necessary distinction, while numerous popular books [...] have led many people now to enthusiasm [...] now to alarmed reactions.» I can only make these words my own, and I add the conclusion of that book, which I find equally illuminating: «While on the ethical plane it is easy to understand, at least at first glance, what there is in us that is not in those marvelous algorithms, understanding what our cognitive resources have more than the resources of AI (and I am not speaking only of current ones) is a difficult task, and to face it one must refer to notions of logic and mathematics that, it seems, many prefer to ignore or set aside in order to guarantee themselves a broader audience.» These conclusions, which I share, should also be taken as a warning. Why don't logic and mathematics reach a broader audience? The answer is banally simple:

because understanding logic and mathematics is for the few and by the few. And yet, anyone who reaches the High School Diploma should have studied mathematics for 12 years. How is it possible that after 12 years of uninterrupted study of such an important subject—one to which the school system at every level devotes a substantial number of teaching hours—people are so refractory toward it? The issue, as is easy to sense, slips immediately from the theoretical, logical, and mathematical level to the educational one. It is not the task of this brief intervention of mine to highlight the “flaws” of the teaching of mathematics in our schools also because, in my view, the problem is not so much “inside” the schools, but upstream of them: in an instructional conception and in a pedagogical vision of learning (and therefore also of teaching) that has gradually spread while, in parallel, becoming impoverished and trivialized over the last decades. Artificial intelligence can help willing teachers and students undertake a path in the opposite direction, the only one—in

my view—possible if we want, as Peruzzi says, «to understand what our cognitive resources have more than the resources of AI.»

The approach I propose, in the final analysis, is psycho-cognitive—or, to be more precise, meta-psycho-cognitive. The influence that artificial intelligence will exert on our lives from here on will be enormous; it is not something we can opt out of. Ultimately the decision is whether to be passive or to try to manage the process. In the didactic and pedagogical realm there are enormous potentials and equally great risks. Although pointing out dangers is always useful, I do not believe that in this case it is sufficient to avoid them, just as hearing the roar of a waterfall does not help you avoid falling into it if you are swimming in the middle of the river. I instead consider it more fruitful to move in the opposite direction, trying to exploit the opportunities—which are not few—that this technology provides us in the direction of improving ourselves and future generations.

ⁱ The original version of this study was authored in Italian and published on the website of the Italian National Research Council (CNR), accessible via the following link: <http://eprints.bice.rm.cnr.it/23511/>. Additionally, the Author's related text on artificial intelligence (P. Fabiani, *Critical Thinking Engineering*, IIC, Florence, 2025) is also freely available for consultation at this link: <https://zenodo.org/records/17496696> or on Academia.edu: https://www.academia.edu/144769698/Paolo_Fabiani_Critical_Thinking_Engineering_Note_per_un_uso_consapevole_dell'intelligenza_artificiale.

ⁱⁱ Consider, for example, what Alberto Peruzzi writes: “The emphasis Flavell (1976) placed on self-reflection, self-monitoring, and self-regulation, as task-directed activities, nevertheless has its roots in Piagetian thought—of which Flavell was among the most acute interpreters in America, as his monograph on Piaget attests: Flavell (1963). The idea is this: to become more aware of the learning process in order to learn better. How? By repeatedly checking the progress made and making adjustments to the strategies being followed. Thus, metacognition does not boil down to mere awareness but requires initiative; and it is an initiative that, if cultivated, goes far beyond the school setting, because it educates us to move from a superficial consideration of the questions life puts to us to a care for the quality of our answers.” *Metacognizione e linguaggio*, in *Sulla metacognizione*, a cura di A. Mariani e D. Sarsini, CLUEB Bologna 2006, pp. 117-148.

ⁱⁱⁱ We refer here to an Italian word, as the original version of this study was written in Italian.

^{iv} For a long time there has been debate about whether new technologies are useful in learning. The issue is certainly articulated, complex, and multifaceted, and things that may look similar but are not must be kept carefully distinct. It is one thing to recognize that AI helps as a tool, or that it inhibits—or can inhibit—certain cognitive competencies or capacities; it is another matter to assess whether, how, when, and to what extent new technologies help (or do not help) improve school study. In this regard, it is worth quoting what Antonio Calvani argues, since he clarifies one of these aspects particularly well. «We should point out the naïveté that innovation enthusiasts fall into, supporters of the principle that schools must adapt to the new generation. The argument, in summary, is this: digital natives are developing new cognitive traits and behavioral practices as a result of their intimate coexistence with new technologies; the school, which still reflects and conveys traditional cultural models, must adapt to these new demands; teachers must welcome young people’s requests, in a certain sense learn from them. The result will be a strong increase in motivation and therefore in learning. This is an analysis that belongs to the mythologies of the digital: it is not supported by evidence on the one hand, and it diminishes the educational value of school on the other. The literature does not show such strong pressure from the new generations to use more digital technologies at school (if anything, this is a need of adults and institutions, projected onto young people for other reasons). The evidence then shows that the learning benefits of introducing technologies are limited, must be identified case by case (cf. ch. 3), and that it is rather the methods used by teachers that make the difference. The data themselves on the digital behaviors of the new generations show that, despite the enormous amount of time they spend with new devices, their skills—even those of a strictly technical nature—are generally fragmented and of low qualitative level, while the cognitive and ethical dimensions are decidedly lacking, essential components if we are to speak of true digital competence.» A. Calvani, *Mente e media - Spazi e forme di interazione cognitiva per apprendere* in *Le tecnologie educative - Criteri per una scelta basata su evidenze*, G. Bonaiuti, A. Calvani, L. Menichetti, G. Vivanet, Carocci Editore, Roma, 2017.

^v In the field of effective teaching methodologies and in techniques for memorization and mental calculation, there are plenty of snake-oil salesmen on the one hand, and people improvising on the other. The former “sell” alleged methods for studying less and passing exams; the latter (teachers and educators who approach these topics out of sincere intellectual and professional interest) often fall into a kind of naïveté, assuming that reading a book is enough to truly master “the subject.” It is not. From personal experience I can say with confidence that having memorization techniques taught to children by an expert with years—decades, in my case—of continuous study, versus having them taught by someone who has read only one or two books and has done little or no practice on themselves, makes a substantial difference.

^{vi} Regarding the relationship between the use of technology in studying and cognitive overload, consider:: A. Calvani, *Mente e media - Spazi e forme di interazione cognitiva per apprendere* in *Le tecnologie educative - Criteri per una scelta basata su evidenze*, G. Bonaiuti, A. Calvani, L. Menichetti, G. Vivanet, Roma, Carocci Editore, 2017, pp. 5, 20, 63, 72-74; F. Landriscina, *Carico cognitivo e impiego della tecnologia per apprendere*, in A. Calvani (a cura di), *Tecnologia, scuola, processi cognitivi*, F. Angeli, Milano 2006, pp. 55-78; A. Calvani, *Come fare una lezione efficace*, Carocci, Roma, 2014, pp.

50, 80-81, 94-96, (especially pages 80-81 should be considered in relation specifically to the theme of attention); G. Bonaiuti A. Calvani M, Ranieri, *Fondamenti di didattica - Teoria e prassi dei dispositivi formativi*, Carocci, Roma, 2016.

^{vii} I often use this example when I teach lessons, lead seminars, and run projects with classes, because I have realized it is especially clear and easy to grasp both for students and for teachers. This illustration is theoretically supported by Baddeley's *multicomponent model* (A. Baddeley & G. Hitch, 1974; A. Baddeley, 2000). More specifically, maintaining the verbal trace (the words just spoken) is handled by the *Phonological Loop*, the subsystem responsible for processing linguistic information. Coordinating the monitoring of the present with future planning, by contrast, is a function of the *Central Executive*. It is crucial to emphasize that this system operates with limited capacity: cognitive resources are not infinite and, if the information load (cognitive load) exceeds the threshold of what can be managed, or if articulatory rehearsal is interrupted, the memory trace decays, compromising the coherence of the discourse.

^{viii} Much has been written and discussed about metacognition in recent decades. Among the many available texts, I will henceforth limit my references to two authors already cited in the previous pages: Alberto Peruzzi and Antonio Calvani. Specifically, I refer to the following texts: A. Peruzzi, *Metacognizione e linguaggio*, in *Sulla metacognizione*, a cura di A. Mariani e D.Sarsini, Bologna, CLUEB, 2006, pp. 117-148; A. Peruzzi, *Il significato inesistente*, Firenze, FUP, 2004; A. Calvani, *Mente e media - Spazi e forme di interazione cognitiva per apprendere* in *Le tecnologie educative - Criteri per una scelta basata su evidenze*, G. Bonaiuti, A. Calvani, L. Menichetti, G. Vivanet, Roma, Carocci Editore, 2017; A. Calvani, *Evidence-based education. Perché è necessario orientare l'istruzione verso una cultura dell'evidenza*, in *Nuova Secondaria*, Roma, Edizioni Studiorum, 2025, pp. 32-39; A. Calvani, *Progettazione didattica e Intelligenza Artificiale - Indicazioni nazionali e Unità di Apprendimento*, Roma, Anicia 2025; A. Peruzzi, *Molto rumore per qualcosa*, Metilene, Pistoia, 2024.